

Developing of the Cocktail-Types Tomato - New Direction in Breeding in Uzbekistan

Author(s): ¹EKATERINA LYAN, ²VERONIKA KIM

Abstract:

This article provides information of the results of testing 6 varieties of cocktail-types of tomato selection of the Scientific Research Institute of Vegetable and Melon Crops and Potatoes in greenhouses of the Tashkent region. The cultivars were evaluated by yield, average weight of fruits, biochemical composition of fruits, transportability, and resistance to diseases.

Keywords: varieties and hybrids, cocktail-tomatoes, yield, transportability, disease resistance,

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About Author

Author(s): ¹EKATERINA LYAN, ²VERONIKA KIM

¹Head of the Laboratory of Vegetable Growing in Protected Soil, Ph.D., Research Institute of Vegetable and Melon Crops and Potatoes, Uzbekistan

²Ph.D., Institute of Genetics and Experimental Plant Biology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan. Email: v.veronika_9@mail.ru

Introduction

Tomato is one of the popular vegetable crops in Uzbekistan, grown in greenhouses, which occupies 50-55% of the total cultivated area. Along with large-fruited tomatoes in recent years, small-fruited cherry tomatoes and medium-fruited cocktail tomatoes are in great demand in our Republic. The fruits of the cocktail-type tomato are distinguished by an attractive presentation, have a high nutritional value, contain vitamins, organic acids, and mineral salts.

Methods

Developing of cocktail types of varieties and hybrids of tomatoes is a new direction in the selection of greenhouse tomatoes, they differ from other species and varieties in their size and color of the fruit. The fruits remain on the clusters for a long time. They are small, weighing only 40-60 g [6].

Actually, single cocktail-type of greenhouse tomato has not been zoned in our Republic yet. In this connection, the selection for the creation of local cocktail varieties of greenhouse tomato will be timely and very relevant.

In recent years, the employees of the laboratory of greenhouse vegetable growing have been working on the selection of cherry tomatoes, created and zoned varieties, cherry Marvarid (2014), cherry F₁ Umid (2019), F₁ Yantarniy (Amber) (2020), and also work is underway to create cocktail types of tomatoes based on lines from interspecific crosses [2,3,4].

Experimental Results

In the process of the experiments 2018-2019, carried out in spring film greenhouses, the following hybrid cocktail combinations obtained in previous years were planted in comparison with the Marvarid cherry standard; F₁ L-19-11x Marvarid; F₁ L-20-06x Marvarid; F₁ L-20-08 x Marvarid; F₁L-20-06 x L-20-08; F₁ L-19-11 x L-20-08.

The accounting plot area is 8 m², 3-fold repetition, planting scheme 120 + 80 x 40 cm, the culture was carried out in one stem. Tomato seedlings were prepared in 2 film greenhouses.

Planted in a permanent place with 55-day old seedlings [1].

Phenological observations and biometric measurements were carried out on the 90th, 120th, and 150th days from mass shoots (Table 1).

As can be seen from table 1, the emergence of mass shoots in all cultivars occurred on days 7-8, the same pattern was observed when the 1st and 5th true leaves appeared, respectively, on days 11-12 and 34-36 days.

The noted pattern is confirmed by the dates of tying the 1st, 2nd and 3rd hand.

Under equal conditions of the microclimate of the soil data during the study of varieties on the 90th, 120th, 150th, day from mass shoots, the highest height of the main stem was observed in F₁ L-20-06 x Marvarid (115, 208 and 235 cm), F₁ L-20- 08 x Marvarid (110, 201 and 230 cm), the smallest was noted in F₁ L-19-11 x Marvarid (105, 182 and 205 cm), the height of the main stem was intermediate in the remaining varieties.

Table 1. Passage of phenophases in tomato cultivars in the spring turnover (2018-2020).

№	Variety samples	The emergence of mass seedlings of days	Number of days before				
			Emergence of leaves		Tying soybean brushes		
			1 th	5 th	1 th	2 th	3 th
St	Cherry Marwarid	8	12	36	54	68	76
1	F ₁ L-19-11 x Marwarid	7	12	35	53	66	75
2	F ₁ L-20-06 x Marwarid	7	12	35	53	66	74
3	F ₁ L-20-08 x Marwarid	7	11	35	53	66	74
4	F ₁ Marwarid x L-20-08	7	11	35	53	66	75
5	F ₁ L-20-06 x L-20-08	7	11	34	52	65	74
6	F ₁ L-19-11 x L-20-08	7	11	34	52	65	74

Another important indicator characterizing the prospects and suitability of a variety, a hybrid is its leafiness, i.e. the number of leaves on the plant (table 2).

Table 2. The number of leaves in the cocktail-type tomato cultivars in the spring turnover, (2018-2020).

№	Сортообразцы	Number of leaves per day; pieces		
		90 th	120 th	150 th
St	Cherry Marwarid	18	31	39
1	F ₁ L-19-11 x Marwarid	21	37	48
2	F ₁ L-20-06 x Marwarid	23	39	49
3	F ₁ L-20-08 x Marwarid	22	40	48
4	F ₁ Marwarid x L-20-08	21	39	42
5	F ₁ L-20-06 x L-20-08	20	38	42
6	F ₁ L-19-11 x L-20-08	21	36	41

It should be noted that the presence of a larger number of leaves in tomato cultivars is a positive trait in breeding; it has been proven that a large number of plant leaves improves carbon nutrition and photosynthesis. In the end, it contributes to an enhanced flowering process, fruit formation, increases productivity and quality product yield.

In our experiments, tomato plants at the end of the growing season reached a height of over 3 meters, thus forming a huge leaf apparatus.

One of the important indicators of the prospects of any variety of tomato is its productivity and quality (Fig. 1).

Figure: 1 Yield and its quality in cocktail-type tomato varieties in the spring turnover (2018-2020).

You can see from Diagram 1 by yield, by the output of marketable products, the following varieties were distinguished: Marvarid x F₁ L-20-08 -12.5 kg / m², F₁ L-19-11 x L-20-08-12.0 kg / m², F₁ L-20-06 x L-20-08-11.7 kg / m², F₁ L-20-06 x Marvarid -11.2 kg / m², the lowest yield was observed in F₁ L-19-11 x Marvarid -10.5 kg / m², for the Cherry standard Marvarid -9.1 kg / m². Since all the studied varieties belong to the group of medium-fruited, the average fruit weight in all the studied varieties ranged from 38-53 g, while the marketable output of all the studied samples was 98%. The smallest average difference was NSR05 - 1.6

And, according to the biochemical composition, the content of total sugar, ascorbic acid, as well as the accumulation of nitrate nitrogen, the Cherry standard Marvarid was released, respectively 4.9%, 24.8 mg% and 110 mg / kg and did not exceed the MPC (150 mg / kg per 1 kg of fresh tomato fruit [5]).

In cocktail-type varieties, the dry matter content was at the level of 7.2-7.9%, sugars from 3.9-4.5%, ascorbic acid 22.6-24 mg%, nitrate nitrogen from 88.0-100 mg / kg of fresh tomato fruits.

The tasting score for all studied varieties ranged from 4.0-5.0 points.

As it was already noted above, the perceptiveness of any tomato cultivar is determined by its resistance to diseases (Fig. 2).

Figure: 2. Assessment of tomato cultivars for disease resistance (2018-2020).

As can be seen from diagram 1, the most resistant to TMV (tobacco mosaic virus) and brown leaf spot were F1 Marwarid x L-20-08 and F1 L-20-06 x L-20-08-100%, the rest of the samples were affected by tobacco viruses mosaic and brown leaf spot by 2-10.25%.

Analyzing the data obtained, it can be noted that the new medium-fruited hybrid combinations belonging to the cocktail group tested in the hybrid nursery turned out to be very promising in all parameters (yield, taste, biochemical composition of fruits, in appearance, resistance to diseases), which is confirmed by production tests conducted in the farm "E. Muhammad" Tashkent region on an area of 0.1 hectares.

Our experiments were carried out in 3 replicates, the area of the accounting plot was 50 m², the planting scheme was 80x40 cm, and it was formed into one stem (Table 4.).

Table 4. The results of the production test in the farm "E. Muhammad" Tashkent region. (2019-2020).

Nº	Indicators	St cherry Marwarid	F1 Marwarid x L-20-08	F1 L-19-11 x L-20-08	F1 L-20-06 x L-20-08
1	Main stem height, cm (120th day)	215	228	235	236
2	Marketable yield kg / m ²	9,8	11,8	12,5	12,8
3	% to St	100	120	128	131
4	Average fruit weight, g	24	45	49	55
5	Fruit shape index	County.	County.	Oval.	Elongation
6	Fruit color	Red	Red	Chocolate	Orange
7	Dry matter,%	6,5	6,5	7,6	7,5
8	Total sugar,%	3,4	3,0	3,6	3,5

9	Ascorbic acid, mg%	22,4	23,1	22,8	23,0
10	Nitrate nitrogen, mg / kg	90	100	98	105
11	Damage rate, TMV%	0	0	0	0
12	Brown leaf spot, points	0	0	0	0
13	Transportability, points	6,0	7,0	7,0	7,0
14	Tasting assessment, points	4,8	4,0	4,0	4,5

Conclusion

As a result of the study, for the first time in Uzbekistan in the field of protected ground, a series of varieties and hybrids of cocktail-type tomatoes with a weight of 40-60 g with different colors of fruits: red, yellow, orange, pink, brown (chocolate) and striped, as well as the shape of the fruit will be created - round, elongated, pear-shaped, plum-shaped, finger-shaped with high taste and marketability.

Production and environmental tests of promising cocktail-types tomatoes of 3 samples: F₁ Marvarid x L-20-08, F₁ L-19-11 x L-20-08, F₁ L-20-06 x L-20-08 in comparison with The standard cherry Marvarid turned out to be very promising in all parameters (yield, taste, biochemical composition of fruits, in appearance, disease resistance), which is confirmed by production tests carried out in the farm "E. Muhammad" in Tashkent region.

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